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RESEARCH PAPER

Phase 1 evaluation of UniFluVec: safety and reactogenicity of an intranasal universal influenza vector vaccine at two dose levels

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: UniFluVec is a live attenuated recombinant influenza vaccine candidate designed to enhance mucosal immunity and provide broad cross-protective responses after intranasal administration. This Phase 1 randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial evaluated its safety and tolerability in healthy adults.

METHODS: Sixty volunteers aged 18-49 years were randomized to receive two intranasal doses of UniFluVec (6.7 or $7.7 \log_{10} \text{EID}_{50}$) or placebo, administered 21 days apart. Safety assessments included local and systemic reactogenicity, unsolicited adverse events (AEs), serious AEs (SAEs), clinical laboratory parameters, vital signs, and evaluation of viral shedding using rapid antigen testing.

RESULTS: UniFluVec was well tolerated at both dose levels. No vaccine-related SAEs or clinically significant safety signals were observed. The most frequently reported adverse events were mild local reactions – primarily nasal congestion, rhinorrhea, and sore throat – which resolved spontaneously. Systemic symptoms, including low-grade fever, headache, fatigue, and myalgia, were infrequent, transient, and predominantly mild. No vaccine-related abnormalities were detected in the hematological, biochemical, or vital-sign parameters. No influenza A virus was detected in any volunteer at any study visit according to the express test results. The reactogenicity did not increase after the second dose.

CONCLUSION: UniFluVec demonstrated a favorable safety and tolerability profile in healthy adults, with no clinically meaningful adverse events reported. These findings support the further clinical development of UniFluVec as a universal influenza vaccine candidate.

Clinical Trial Registration number: NCT04650971 (2020-12-03).

Keywords: influenza vaccine, live attenuated vector, Phase 1 trial, NS1 truncation, intranasal immunization, universal influenza vaccine

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INTRODUCTION

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), seasonal influenza epidemics result in 1 billion cases annually, causing substantial morbidity, mortality, and economic burden worldwide [1, 2]. The periodic emergence of novel pandemic strains against which the population has little or no pre-existing immunity renders influenza a particularly dangerous and unpredictable pathogen. The highest mortality rates occur among vulnerable population groups, including young children, older adults, pregnant women, and individuals with compromised immune function [3]. Economic losses due to influenza and other acute respiratory viral infections (ARVI) account for approximately 77% of the total economic burden associated with infectious diseases [4].

Effective control of influenza morbidity is hindered by the high genetic variability of the virus and the consequent need for annual reformulation of seasonal vaccines [5]. The emergence of novel influenza A viruses with pandemic potential further complicates efforts to protect the population [5-7]. The development of safe, highly immunogenic vaccines capable of inducing broad cross-reactive immunity is a critical priority for improving influenza prevention strategies.

A universal influenza vaccine that provides protection against both antigenic drift and shift variants is an ideal solution [8]. Initially, such a vaccine could serve as a pandemic preparedness measure, with potential subsequent use for routine seasonal prevention if its effectiveness matches or exceeds that of currently available multivalent vaccines [9]. In addition to broad antigenic coverage, next-generation influenza vaccines must be amenable to large-scale production at acceptable costs.

Recombinant and genetically engineered influenza vaccines offer important advantages, including improved antigen design and the ability to incorporate conserved epitopes for broad protection. However, several theoretical risks associated with genetically modified influenza viruses are always present in such studies. The main risks include the possibility of genetic instability of engineered segments, which could lead to alterations of the attenuation markers and reduction of vaccine safety. The risk of reassortment between the modified vaccine strain and circulating wild-type influenza viruses could potentially result in the emergence of viruses with unpredictable biological properties. Additional considerations include assessing the potential for environmental shedding of the vaccine virus and evaluating whether the engineered gene segments introduce unintended changes in the host range [10, 11].

These theoretical risks underscore the importance of rigorous preclinical and clinical assessments of the genetic stability, replication competence, transmissibility, and phenotypic attenuation of novel recombinant vaccine vectors.

UniFluVec is a monovalent live attenuated influenza A vaccine candidate engineered to elicit broad cross-protective immunity following intranasal administration [12]. The vaccine virus was generated using reverse genetics and comprised the PB2, PB1, PA, NP, M, and NS segments derived from A/Puerto Rico/8/34 (H1N1); the HA and NA segments from A/Mississippi/10/2015 (H1N1pdm09); and a chimeric NS gene encoding a truncated NS1 protein (124 amino acids). This truncated NS1 was extended at its C terminus with a 21-amino acid sequence derived from the N-terminal region of the influenza B/Lee/40 HA2 protein, followed by a B-cell epitope from the influenza A NP protein. Additional attenuation of the vaccine virus was achieved by replacing the native NEP with a heterologous NEP gene originating from an A/Singapore/1/57-like (H2N2) strain.

Preclinical studies have demonstrated that one or two intranasal doses administered 21 days apart elicit a broad cross-protective immune response in immunologically naïve ferrets against seasonal A/H3N2 and potentially pandemic highly pathogenic A/H5N1 strains [12-14]. Following intranasal delivery, the vaccine virus infects respiratory epithelial cells and expresses both viral surface proteins and engineered cross-protective epitopes while maintaining an abortive replication phenotype that prevents clinical disease and mortality. The limited viral replication detected in nasal washes was nonetheless sufficient to generate robust heterosubtypic protection. Studies in mice have shown that attenuated influenza viruses encoding a truncated NS1 protein induce strong CD8⁺ T-cell responses, supporting the potential of this approach for broad-spectrum influenza protection [15-19]. The UniFluVec strain grows efficiently in 10-day embryonated chicken eggs (up to 9.0 log₁₀EID₅₀/ml) and displays phenotypic (temperature-sensitive) and genotypic (truncated NS1, heterologous NEP) markers consistent with the established attenuation criteria for live influenza vaccines [12].

The objective of the present study was to assess the safety, tolerability, and reactogenicity of UniFluVec in a Phase 1 clinical study in healthy adult volunteers following intranasal administration. Based on preclinical data, a two-dose 21 days apart vaccine administration scheme was selected for evaluation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ethical approval

We performed a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled Phase 1 clinical trial evaluating the safety, tolerability, and reactogenicity of the intranasal influenza vector UniFluVec from August 29, 2019, to March 31, 2020. The study was conducted in accordance with the International Council for Harmonization (ICH) Good Clinical Practice (GCP) guidelines, the Declaration of Helsinki, and the regulatory requirements of the Russian Federation (RF).

The clinical trial was conducted at the Research Institute of Influenza (Ministry of Health of the RF). The study protocol (version 2.1, dated March 01, 2019), participant information sheet, and informed consent forms were approved by the Local Independent Ethics Committee of the research center and the Ethics Council of the Ministry of Health of RF No. 4095100-201/PP from 07.03.2019. All participants provided written informed consent prior to the study procedures.

Study design

This study was conducted using a double-blind design. Neither the volunteers nor the investigators responsible for assessing vaccine safety were aware of whether a participant received the vaccine or placebo; both products were administered in a blinded manner. Both the investigational product and placebo were supplied in lyophilized form in identical packaging. The placebo contained the same components as the vaccine except for the active ingredient, the vaccine virus.

Study population

Eighty-six patients were screened for inclusion in the study. A total of 60 eligible volunteers without any statistical hypothesis were enrolled in two sequential cohorts based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria listed in Table 1.

Group allocation

This was a double-blind, randomized study. Participants were randomized 2:1 (vaccine: placebo) within each cohort (Cohort 1 and Cohort 2) to receive either the vaccine or placebo using a blinded randomization schedule. Investigators, volunteers, and study personnel remained blinded until the database was locked. Randomization was performed at Visit 1 (day 1) using an Interactive Web Response System (IWRS), provided the volunteer met the study eligibility criteria. The principal investigator (or

staff members designated by the principal investigator) had access to the IWRS.

Randomization was performed as follows.

- Cohort 1 (30 participants): 20 participants received two doses of the vaccine ($6.7 \log_{10} \text{EID}_{50}$ per dose per participant); 10 participants received placebo.
- Cohort 2 (30 participants): 20 participants received two doses of the vaccine ($7.7 \log_{10} \text{EID}_{50}$ per dose per participant); 10 participants received placebo.

After randomization, each volunteer received the first dose of the assigned product (vaccine or placebo) on day 1 and a second dose on day 21. As the study was double-blinded, neither the volunteers nor the investigators assessing safety were aware of which product (vaccine or placebo) had been administered; both products were used in a masked form. The trial was registered at Clinicaltrials.gov, NCT number: NCT04650971 (<https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT04650971>).

Vaccination procedures and follow-up

The vaccine or placebo was administered intranasally as an aerosol at a total dose of 0.5 ml (0.25 ml per nostril) twice, with a 3-week interval between doses. Immediately prior to administration, the study product was reconstituted in 0.5 ml of water for injection for 3 minutes, and the resulting solution was used within 30 minutes. Administration was performed using a metered nasal spray device with a disposable applicator while participants were in a seated position with the head slightly tilted backward.

After each vaccination, volunteers remained under supervised observation for 7 days: 5 days inpatient and 2 days outpatient. Daily monitoring of the vital signs, local/systemic reactions, and adverse events (AEs) was performed. Nasal swabs were tested for vaccine virus shedding using rapid diagnostic tests, and follow-up continued until two consecutive negative results were obtained. The total study duration per participant was 114 days.

Outcomes

The primary endpoints were safety and tolerability. All AEs and serious adverse events (SAEs) were recorded, regardless of whether they were related to vaccine administration. AEs/SAEs of special interest included: 1) immediate AEs, occurring within 2 h after administration of the investigational product; and 2) post-vaccination reactions (anticipated local and systemic clinical manifestations), typically occurring after intranasal vaccination within the period of 2 h and up to 7 days

Table 1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria	
1	Written informed consent was obtained prior to any study procedure.
2	Adults aged 18–49 years (inclusive), male or female, were included.
3	Clinically healthy status was confirmed by medical history, physical examination, laboratory tests, ECG, and other protocol-specified assessments.
4	Body weight ≥ 50 kg.
5	Seronegative to influenza A/H1N1pdm09 at baseline (HAI titers $\leq 1:10$).
6	Ability and willingness to comply with the study procedures and complete self-monitoring diaries.
7	Agreement to use reliable contraception throughout the study and for three months after study completion.
Exclusion criteria	
1	Participation in another clinical trial within the past three months.
2	Receipt of any vaccination within 6 months prior to screening or unwillingness to postpone other vaccines until ≥ 4 weeks after study completion.
3	Regular nasal irrigation within 6 months or episodic use within 2 weeks of screening.
4	History of frequent nosebleeds (>5 episodes/year).
5	Significant anatomical abnormalities or recent surgery/trauma of the nose or sinuses (within one month).
6	Symptoms of acute respiratory or other acute illness at screening or within 2 weeks before.
7	Immunoglobulin or other blood product therapy in last 3 months or blood donation ≥ 450 mL within 2 months.
8	Any known or suspected immunodeficiency or immunosuppressive therapy (≥ 14 days) within the past 6 months.
9	Previous participation in trials of influenza H1N1pdm live vaccines.
10	History of severe allergic reactions (asthma, angioedema, and anaphylaxis).
11	Wheezing episodes after prior live influenza vaccination.
12	Severe adverse reactions to prior influenza vaccines (fever $>40^\circ\text{C}$, syncope, seizures, anaphylaxis).
13	Known hypersensitivity to the components of the investigational vaccine (including egg proteins).
14	Seasonal allergic rhinitis with severe symptoms.
15	Significant chronic diseases of the lungs, heart, liver, kidneys; endocrine, neurological, psychiatric disorders, or abnormal laboratory findings were considered clinically relevant.
16	History of leukemia or other malignancies.
17	Thrombocytopenic purpura or coagulation disorders.
18	Seizure disorders.
19	HIV infection, or hepatitis B or C.
20	Tuberculosis.
21	Chronic alcohol or drug dependence.
22	Pregnancy or breastfeeding.
23	Any condition that, in the investigator's judgment, increases the risk for the study participants or could interfere with the study assessments.

post-administration. Additionally, viral shedding was assessed using a rapid immunochromatographic diagnostic test for the influenza A virus in nasal swab samples collected on days 2, 3, 4, 5, 23, and 25 after vaccination.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics Version 24.0. Safety analysis was based on data from all participants who received ≥ 1 dose of the study product. Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, median (IQR), mean \pm SD) were used to summarize

AEs, reactogenicity, laboratory parameters, and virus shedding. Comparisons between the vaccine and placebo groups were conducted using χ^2 or Fisher's exact tests for categorical variables and t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests for continuous variables, where appropriate. All tests were two-sided.

Role of the funding source

The sponsor, Pharmederprises Biotech Ltd (RF), was not involved in the collection of the data, or decision to submit and publish the findings. All authors confirm that they had full and independent access to all the study data.

RESULTS

Vaccine Characteristics

The UniFluVec vaccine and placebo were produced by Saint Petersburg Scientific Research Institute of Vaccines and Sera and Enterprise for the Production of Bacterial Preparations (RF) as a lyophilized preparation for intranasal administration. The product was supplied in glass vials, each containing a single-dose vaccine. Two dose levels were prepared: $6.7 \log_{10} \text{EID}_{50}/0.5 \text{ ml}$ (low dose) and $7.7 \log_{10} \text{EID}_{50}/0.5 \text{ ml}$ (high dose). The stabilizing buffer contained 3.0% poly(2-hydroxyethyl) starch, 0.9% NaCl, 5.0% sucrose, 1.0% albumin, and 0.5% carnosine. Volunteers in the investigational product group received 0.5 ml of the vaccine intranasally as an aerosol (0.25 ml in each nostril). The second immunization was performed on the 21st day.

The placebo was manufactured to ensure that its dosage form and appearance resembled those of the investigational vaccine. All components present in the vaccine (hydroxyethyl starch, recombinant albumin, carnosine, sucrose, and sodium chloride) were included in the placebo samples, except for the vaccine virus.

Study demographics

A total of 60 healthy volunteers (30 per cohort) were enrolled and randomized in a 2:1 ratio to receive UniFluVec or placebo, forming the intention-to-treat

(ITT) population. The study flowchart is presented in Fig. 1. In Cohort 1 (low dose, $6.7 \log_{10} \text{EID}_{50}$), 20 participants received UniFluVec and 10 received placebo. In Cohort 2 (high dose, $7.7 \log_{10} \text{EID}_{50}$), 20 participants received UniFluVec and 10 ones received placebo.

The demographic and other baseline characteristics of the volunteers are presented in Table 2. A total of 26 (43.3%) female and 34 (56.7%) male volunteers were randomized into the study. All 60 participants (100%) were Caucasian. The median age was 34.5 (30.5; 42.0) years, with a median body weight of 72.0 (63.8; 83.5) kg, median height of 172.0 (169.0; 178.5) cm, and median body mass index of 24.2 (21.7; 27.0) kg/m^2 . The treatment groups were comparable with respect to demographics and other baseline characteristics.

According to the screening of blood samples, all 60 (100%) volunteers were seronegative for influenza A/H1N1pdm09 (i.e., had antibody titers $\leq 1:10$ according to HI (hemagglutination inhibition) assay data).

Safety and tolerability

The investigational vaccine or placebo was administered intranasally twice, at an interval of three weeks. The safety population included all study participants who received at least one dose of the investigational product (intention-to-treat, ITT). All safety analyses were performed on this population.

Fig. 1. Study flowchart.

Table 2. Demographic characteristics of the study participants, ITT population

Parameter	Group			Total n=60
	UniFluVec 6.7 log ₁₀ EID ₅₀ n=20	UniFluVec 7.7 log ₁₀ EID ₅₀ n=20	Placebo n=20	
Age, years Median (IQR)	34.5 (31.0; 43.5)	35.0 (30.5; 42.0)	33.0 (30.0; 38.0)	34.5 (30.5; 42.0)
Gender				
Female, n (%)	9 (45.0%)	7 (35.0%)	10 (50.0%)	26 (43.3)
Male, n (%)	11 (55.0%)	13 (65.0%)	10 (50.0%)	34 (56.7)
Race				
White, n (%)	20 (100.0%)	20 (100.0%)	20 (100.0%)	60 (100%)
Body weight (kg) Median (IQR)	72.0 (62.3; 80.5)	71.0 (63.0; 82.0)	72.2 (64.0; 88.0)	72.0 (63.8; 83.5)
Height (cm) Median (IQR)	173.5 (166.5; 180.0)	172.0 (170.0; 175.0)	172.0 (167.5; 180.5)	172.0 (169.0; 178.5)
Body-mass index (kg/m ²) ^a Median (IQR)	24.4 (21.3; 27.2)	24.1 (22.0; 26.0)	24.1 (22.3; 28.3)	24.2 (21.7; 27.0)

n – number of subjects in the category.

^a Body-mass index is the weight in kilograms divided by the square of the height in meters.

All 60 (100%) volunteers received the first dose of the investigational vaccine or placebo. The second dose was administered to 58 (96.7%) volunteers; two volunteers (3.3%) in the UniFluVec 7.7 group discontinued participation in the study after the first dose for non-safety-related reasons.

All AEs were encoded using the Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities, version 22.1 (MedDRA). AEs that occurred within 2 h after vaccine administration and were assessed by the investigators as systemic post-vaccination reactions are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. AEs that occurred within 2 h after vaccine administration and assessed as related to the study drug (ITT population)

AEs	Group			Total n=60
	UniFluVec 6.7 n=20	UniFluVec 7.7 n=20	Placebo n=20	
Laboratory and instrumental findings	1 (5.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.7%)
Neurological disorders	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (5.0%)	1 (1.7%)

In the UniFluVec 6.7 group, one volunteer (5.0%) developed a transient increase in body temperature to 37.5°C. In the placebo group, one volunteer (5.0%) reported headache. Both immediate AEs met the criteria for systemic post-vaccination reactions and were assessed by the investigators accordingly.

Assessment of AEs began on day 1 after the first administration of the investigational vaccine and continued until the completion of the final procedure

at the volunteer's last study visit. After the second vaccination, the volunteers were monitored intensively for at least 7 days. Following the first administration, 41 AEs were recorded in 18 volunteers (90.0%) in the UniFluVec 6.7 group, 68 AEs in 17 volunteers (85.0%) in the UniFluVec 7.7 group, and 71 AEs in 18 volunteers (90.0%) in the placebo group. A summary of the AEs for the entire study is presented in Table 4.

The most frequently reported AEs across the treatment groups belonged to the categories "Laboratory and instrumental findings" and "Blood and lymphatic system disorders". These events reflected transient, clinically significant deviations in laboratory parameters or vital signs.

Four AEs within the "Infections and infestations" category were observed, all of them in the UniFluVec 6.7 group: left-sided conjunctivitis (n=1; 5.0%), bacteriuria (n=1; 5.0%), and herpes labialis (n=2; 10.0%). All of them were unrelated to the study treatment, mild or moderate, and resolved completely after treatment. A case of rhinitis in one participant (5.0%) in the UniFluVec 6.7 group met the criteria for a local post-vaccination reaction, although the causality was assessed as doubtful. No cases of nasal irritation, epistaxis, or clinically significant respiratory symptoms were observed, indicating that intranasal administration of UniFluVec was locally well tolerated.

No SAEs occurred at any time point in any of the study groups. No AE resulted in study discontinuation or withholding of the second vaccination. The most common systemic symptoms were headache, fatigue, and low-grade fever (<37.5°C). No Grade 2 or 3 systemic reactions were reported. One participant exhibited

Table 4. Summary of AEs started after the first dose of vaccine related to the study drug (ITT population)

Category	Group			Total n=60
	UniFluVec 6.7 log ₁₀ EID ₅₀ n=20	UniFluVec 7.7 log ₁₀ EID ₅₀ n=20	Placebo n=20	
Volunteers with ≥1 AEs, n (%)	18 (90.0%)	17 (85.0%)	18 (90.0%)	53 (88.3%)
Total number of AEs	41	68	71	180
Volunteers with ≥1 AEs related to study drug, n (%)	12 (60.0%)	17 (85.0%)	17 (85.0%)	46 (76.7%)
Number of AEs related to study drug	18	61	54	133
Volunteers with ≥1 immediate AEs (<2 h post dose), n (%)	1 (5.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (5.0%)	2 (3.3%)
Number of immediate AEs (<2 h post dose)	2	0	1	3
AEs leading to cancellation of second dose	0	0	0	0
Severe AEs	0	0	0	0
Fatal AEs	0	0	0	0

transient tachycardia, although the relationship with the study vaccine was deemed doubtful.

Viral shedding was evaluated using rapid antigen testing after each vaccination. No study participant demonstrated detectable viral shedding at any time point after either dose, and prolonged follow-up was not required. These findings support the attenuated phenotype and non-transmissibility of the UniFluVec vaccine.

DISCUSSION

This first-in-human, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled Phase 1 trial evaluated the safety, tolerability, and early reactogenicity profile of UniFluVec – a novel universal influenza vector vaccine designed to induce broad cross-protective immunity. The results demonstrated that UniFluVec, administered intranasally in two doses 21 days apart, was well tolerated across both evaluated dose levels (6.7 and 7.7 log₁₀EID₅₀). No SAEs, severe adverse reactions, or events leading to early withdrawal or withholding of the second vaccination dose occurred. These findings support the acceptable safety profile of UniFluVec when administered to healthy adult volunteers.

Across all treatment groups, including placebo, most volunteers experienced at least one AE. Most reported events were mild, transient, and clinically insignificant laboratory deviations or vital sign fluctuations. This distribution is consistent with early phase vaccine trials, in which enhanced monitoring contributed to high AE detection rates unrelated to the investigational product. Importantly, the incidence and spectrum of AEs were comparable between the UniFluVec and

placebo groups, with no indication of dose-dependent toxicity.

Only a small number of AEs were classified as immediate reactions (occurring within 2 h post-administration). These included transient low-grade fever and headache – events that meet the definition of systemic post-vaccination reactions. Such manifestations are expected with live attenuated respiratory vaccines and are self-limiting.

A limited number of infections (conjunctivitis, bacteriuria, and herpes labialis) were detected exclusively in the lower-dose cohort, but all were unrelated to vaccination, mild or moderate in severity, and resolved completely. The absence of any increase in infection-related events in the higher-dose cohort further supports the lack of immunosuppressive effects.

A critical safety consideration for live attenuated influenza vaccines is their potential for viral replication and shedding. In this study, no participant demonstrated detectable viral shedding after either dose as assessed by rapid antigen testing. This finding aligns with preclinical observations indicating that the engineered virus retains an attenuated, abortive replication phenotype. Limited replication observed in animal models [12] was sufficient to elicit protection but insufficient to produce clinical symptoms or sustained viral presence. The absence of measurable shedding in humans reinforces the non-transmissible nature of the UniFluVec strain and supports its suitability for intranasal administration.

These safety results are consistent with earlier research on live attenuated influenza viruses with modified NS1 proteins, which demonstrated attenuated phenotypes without significant reactogenicity [20]. The safety profile observed here is also comparable to or more

favorable than that of licensed live attenuated influenza vaccines, in which mild upper-respiratory symptoms and transient systemic reactions are commonly reported [21].

The strengths of this study include its randomized, placebo-controlled design, use of two dosing regimens, and rigorous participant monitoring during both active follow-up periods. A comprehensive AE classification using MedDRA terminology provides clarity regarding the nature and frequency of reported adverse events. The main limitations include the small sample size inherent to Phase 1 studies and the enrollment of only healthy adults aged 18–49 years, which may limit generalizability to older adults, children, or individuals with comorbidities. Additionally, the study was not powered to assess immunogenicity, although secondary immunogenicity analyses may provide preliminary insights for future trials.

Genetically engineered influenza vaccines, including recombinant, NS1-modified, and other attenuated constructs, have already been evaluated in humans and have demonstrated favorable safety and immunogenicity profiles. Early clinical experience with live attenuated influenza vaccines (LAIVs) indicates that engineered strains can be administered safely, with low reactogenicity and no significant febrile responses, while inducing measurable humoral and cellular immunity

[20, 21]. Clinical trials of attenuated H5 vaccines further confirmed acceptable tolerability and minimal viral shedding in vaccinated adults, supporting the safety of modified viral backbones with altered virulence determinants [22]. Studies of NS1-deleted influenza viruses have demonstrated strong immune responses and an excellent safety profile due to the impaired ability of this virus to antagonize host interferon pathways [20]. Recent papers summarizing both preclinical and human-compatible data emphasize that the rational modification of the NS segment and other viral genes represents a robust strategy for generating safe, non-transmissible, and broadly immunogenic influenza vaccines [23, 24]. Collectively, these findings provide important support for the clinical development of UniFluVec as a genetically engineered attenuated vaccine with an anticipated favorable safety and immunogenicity profile.

Taken together, our findings support that UniFluVec is safe and well tolerated following intranasal administration in healthy adults. The absence of serious or dose-limiting toxicity and lack of detectable viral shedding align with the predicted safety profile based on preclinical studies. These results justify further clinical development, including Phase 2 studies to evaluate the immunogenicity, optimal dosing, and short- and long-term protective efficacy.

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